
bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for
innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of marine and coastal geohazard

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UAV surveys and methodology for generating shallow water bathymetry

BridgET Project Result 02

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BridgET: Bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of climate change-induced marine and coastal geohazard

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PROJECT RESULT REPORT

02 - UAV surveys and methodology for generating shallow water bathymetry

Introduction

This report presents the second project result of BridgET, focusing on the application of Uncrewed Aerial Systems (UAS) for generating shallow water bathymetry and other UAS key dataset useful for providing seamless 3D models of coastal zones.

Conducted across the three international BridgET Erasmus+ summer schools, the initiative successfully demonstrates innovative methodologies using UAV-based LiDAR and photogrammetry (SfM) to collect spatial datasets in coastal environments.

UAS data were collected at three key sites (Table 1):

- Red Beach, Santorini (Greece) – an eroding cliff site surveyed using LiDAR.
- St. Tecla & Ciclopi Islands, Sicily (Italy) – a coastal area featuring cliffs and cultural heritage, surveyed with both SfM, LiDAR.
- Magoodhoo Harbor and Reef, Maldives – combining aerial and underwater SfM to assess coral reef topography.

The resulting datasets not only supported scientific analysis for hazard assessment for the project partners, but also offer potential for educational outreach through immersive Virtual Reality (VR) models.

Deliverables produced under Project Result 02 include field-acquired datasets, guidelines, a comparative technology matrix for data acquisition in shallow water, and an internal technical report prepared by the professional partner Orthodrone. Together, these outputs provide dataset and both practical and theoretical insights into the use of UAS for mapping and surveying in shallow water and coastal environments. All Deliverables are listed hereafter.

List of Deliverables:

Deliverable 2.1: UAS survey dataset accessible via DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111459>)

Deliverable 2.2: Guidelines for UAV-based shallow water bathymetry

Deliverable 2.3: Comparative matrix showing technological solution for generating 3D models in shallow water

Deliverable 2.4: An internal technical report provided by Orthodrone GmbH, which includes site-specific details, equipment specifications, and best practices developed in the field.

1. Project Result 02 – Deliverables overview

Below is a detailed description of the key deliverables produced as part of the project results. Each deliverable represents a tangible output supporting the objectives and activities carried out during the project lifecycle.

Deliverable 2.1 – UAV Survey Dataset (DOI)

Description: During the field school activities, Orthodrone GmbH acquired a series of experimental datasets using various UAS-based techniques (Table 1). For the purpose of this deliverable, a representative dataset has been selected and published. This dataset can be downloaded as an example of data acquired through LiDAR or Structure-from-Motion (SfM) methodologies, and it is suitable for virtual reality exploration or as a data source for geohazard-related studies for coastal zones. The data is georeferenced and publicly accessible via DOI for future research and replication.

Type of Output: Geospatial Dataset

Language: English

Access/Format: Online (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111459>)

Access Level: Public

Attachment: DOI: [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111459>]

Site Name	Short description	Date of Capture
Red Beach, Santorini, Greece	Red Beach – A cliff affected by erosion. Due to data protection concerns and the involvement of people, only LiDAR was used for surveying.	2022-10-11
Metaxa Mine, Santorini, Greece	Ancient Shoreline Mine Metaxa – A site where Structure from Motion (SfM) and LiDAR data were combined for analysis.	2022-10-10
Vlychada Beach, Santorini, Greece	Geological Site – Features volcanic stratigraphy, surveyed using SfM for future educational purposes.	2022-10-08
Santa Tecla, Sicily	Harbor Site – Includes a geologically important cliff and a historic tower. A combination of LiDAR and SfM was used.	2023-10-05
Ciclopi Islands, Sicily	Rock Formations (Small Islands) – Due to restricted flight authorization time, only LiDAR was conducted. SfM with a smaller UAS and a sonar mounted on a SUP were used in collaboration with Daniel Carlson integrate data seamlessly with our partner’s surveys.	2023-10-06
Magoodhoo Harbor, Maldives	Harbor at Magoodhoo Island, Faafu Atoll – A combination of LiDAR and SfM was applied for teaching purposes.	2024-11-22
Magoodhoo, Reef, Maldives	Coral Reef Survey – Surveyed from the air using LiDAR , along with above-water and underwater SfM . Due to weather conditions and boat availability, only selected sections were surveyed.	2024-11-14

Table 01: BridgET data sets acquired during summer schools by Orthodrone.

Deliverable 2.2 – Guidelines for UAV-based Shallow Water Bathymetry

Description: A practical guide detailing the methodology for conducting UAV surveys in shallow water environments.

Type of Output: Methodological Guide

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document

Access Level: Public

Attachment: Deliverable 2.2 UAV BridgET Guidelines.pdf

Deliverable 2.3 – Technology Comparison Matrix

Description: A comparative matrix summarizing different technological solutions used for generating 3D bathymetric models in shallow water. It evaluates tools based on accuracy, cost, usability, and environmental constraints.

Type of Output: Comparative Table

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document

Access Level: Public

Attachment: Deliverable 2.3 Shallow Water Technologies.pdf

Deliverable 2.4 – Internal Technical Report by Orthodrone GmbH

Description: A detailed technical report developed by Orthodrone GmbH, containing site-specific observations, equipment specifications, and field-tested best practices. This internal document serves as a resource for partners and project stakeholders.

Type of Output: Internal Report

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document

Access Level: Restricted (internal use only)

Attachment: Deliverable 2.4 Orthodrone Internal Report.pdf

Deliverable 2.1
UAV Survey Dataset

DOI: [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111459>]

Deliverable 2.2

Guidelines for UAV-based Shallow Water Bathymetry

Overview: This report provides a practical guide detailing the methodology for conducting UAV surveys in shallow water environments.

1. Introduction

Shallow water environments present a unique set of challenges for bathymetric data acquisition, especially when aiming for high-resolution 3D mapping. Factors such as water turbidity, surface glint, depth variability, and wave dynamics interfere with both acoustic and optical sensors. Nevertheless, UAV-based techniques, especially those leveraging Structure-from-Motion (SfM) and LiDAR, offer promising alternatives when traditional survey methods (e.g., multibeam echo sounders) are impractical or cost-prohibitive.

2. Why Shallow Waters Are Challenging

Mapping and surveying shallow water environments presents a set of unique and often underestimated challenges. These areas, typically including intertidal zones, coastal fringes, lagoons, and estuaries, are highly dynamic and complex both in their physical properties and in terms of accessibility.

One of the primary issues is the limited access for traditional survey platforms, such as vessels or autonomous surface vehicles (ASV). In very shallow zones, especially those near rocky coasts or marshy areas, deploying a boat can be risky or entirely unfeasible. Even small, portable platforms may struggle with unstable terrain or submerged obstacles.

From a technological point of view, the performance of many conventional sensors is therefore severely impacted in shallow water. Acoustic systems such as multibeam or single beam echosounders are indeed optimized for deeper environments; in shallow zones, the narrow water column reduces the effectiveness of beam coverage, increasing noise and decreasing reliability. Moreover, acoustic signals are more sensitive to interference from the bottom substrate and surface conditions in such confined spaces.

Optical systems, that should represent the available alternative, face, however, their own set of complications. Water clarity is in particular a crucial limiting factor, increased turbidity or the presence of suspended particles can obstruct visibility and prevent the camera or LiDAR signals from accurately reaching and returning from the seafloor. Similarly, surface glint, cloud cover, and varying light conditions affect the quality and consistency of aerial imagery, especially when using RGB sensors for photogrammetry (i.e.: Structure-from-Motion techniques).

Another key constraint is environmental variability. Shallow coastal waters are often subject to rapid and frequent changes driven by tides, wind, and wave action. These fluctuations can alter the physical properties of the water column (e.g., salinity, temperature) and disrupt data consistency across flights or between sensors. Furthermore, moving water can introduce noise in point cloud generation and make it difficult to maintain geometric accuracy.

Because of these combined factors, shallow water environments require tailored, flexible, and context-specific strategies. A pre-survey environmental assessment is essential in guiding the choice of the most appropriate sensor. In many cases, the geomorphological setting is the primary factor influencing the selected methodology, alongside the desired spatial resolution. UAV-based methods, when carefully

planned, offer a high-resolution and efficient solution that can overcome many of the logistical and technical constraints, allowing access to otherwise unreachable areas. However, this approach also comes with its own limitations, which must be considered during planning and execution.

In summary, shallow water zones, especially nearshore and intertidal areas, are difficult to survey due to:

- Limited access for traditional vessels
- High environmental variability (light, turbidity, waves)
- Depths too shallow for acoustic systems to operate effectively
- Frequent changes in water column properties affecting beam refraction
- Presence of surface glint and cloud cover affecting optical sensors

These conditions demand flexible, high-resolution, and cost-effective data collection strategies, which UAVs are increasingly able to provide.

3. Pre-Survey Environmental Assessment

Prior to any UAV-based survey in shallow water environments, conducting a thorough pre-survey environmental assessment is essential. This step serves as the foundation for selecting the appropriate sensor, defining flight parameters, and ensuring that the acquired data will meet the expected quality standards. Shallow water systems are highly variable in both time and space, and understanding their physical and optical characteristics ahead of time can significantly reduce errors and data loss during acquisition.

One of the first aspects to evaluate is water clarity, which is particularly important when working with optical sensors such as RGB cameras or bathymetric LiDAR. The presence of suspended sediments, organic matter, or algal blooms can reduce visibility and interfere with the accuracy of image-based depth estimation. In such cases, selecting a different method or postponing the survey to a more favourable time may be necessary.

Equally important is assessing the depth range of the target area. Identifying zones where acoustic systems are likely to fail can help determine whether UAV-based photogrammetry or LiDAR might be more effective.

Another critical factor is the type of substrate found on the seafloor. Sandy or rocky bottoms, for example, can offer high visual contrast and texture, which is beneficial for photogrammetric techniques like Structure-from-Motion. In contrast, homogeneous or muddy substrates may lack sufficient visual features to generate reliable 3D reconstructions, leading to data voids or inaccuracies.

The dynamics of the environment must also be considered. Variables such as tidal cycles, wind speed, wave action, and cloud cover can all affect UAV stability and image quality. For instance, excessive wave motion can introduce noise or geometric distortion in the data, while sudden changes in lighting conditions may lead to inconsistencies in reflectance or image sharpness. Selecting optimal survey windows, ideally during calm weather, low tide, and consistent lighting, can help mitigate these effects. The pre-survey assessment should therefore include:

A preliminary site evaluation to assess:

- Water clarity (key for optical sensors): turbidity, glint, suspended matter
- Depth range: identify areas <2m where acoustics might fail
- Substrate type: influences reflectivity and photogrammetric texture
- Environmental dynamics: tides, waves, and wind affecting UAV stability and image quality

The consequent selection of survey methodology that should include:

- Sensor type selection
- Survey timing (e.g., low tide or calm conditions)
- Flight planning and overlap strategies

In summary, the pre-survey assessment is not simply a checklist, but a strategic process that allows surveyors to adapt their methodology to the specific characteristics of the site. By understanding the

environmental constraints and selecting the right tools accordingly, it becomes possible to maximize data quality and minimize both technical and logistical risks.

4. Choosing the Right Sensor and Method

Sensor/Method	Platform	Pros	Cons
Photogrammetry (SfM)	UAV (optical camera)	Low-cost, good resolution, photorealistic output	Needs ground control, affected by turbidity/glint
Bathymetric LiDAR	UAV or airborne	Penetrates water column, fast area coverage	High cost, affected by water clarity and light
Satellite-Derived (SDB)	Satellite	Wide coverage, public data, photorealistic	Low resolution, accuracy depends on processing, turbidity-sensitive

Note: SfM is especially suited for very shallow, calm, and clear water environments, where traditional acoustic systems (e.g., echo sounders) are impractical due to depth limitations or access issues, and where LiDAR systems may be too costly or limited by water clarity. While SfM requires optimal light and visibility, it offers a low-cost and flexible alternative in areas otherwise difficult to reach with vessel-based or airborne platforms.

5. Resolution Needs and Survey Design

One of the key decisions when planning a UAV-based bathymetric survey is determining the appropriate spatial resolution, which should align with both the objectives of the study and the physical constraints of the site. The desired level of detail influences not only the choice of sensor but also flight planning, data volume, and processing requirements.

For high-resolution applications, such as habitat mapping, coastal engineering, or virtual reality (VR) modeling, sub-meter resolution is typically required. In these cases, Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry is particularly effective, especially when combined with high-resolution RGB cameras and a well-designed flight plan that ensures dense image overlap. Ground control points (GCPs) are essential in these contexts to achieve the geometric accuracy needed for producing reliable 3D models. High-resolution surveys, however, require more detailed planning, generate larger datasets, and demand greater computing power during post-processing.

Conversely, medium-resolution outputs, in the range of 1 to 2 meters, are generally sufficient for broader-scale analyses such as coastal risk assessments, change detection studies, or land-sea integration in coastal planning. These resolutions may be achieved using LiDAR, particularly in areas where water clarity is sufficient to allow laser penetration to the seafloor. Alternatively, they can result from a hybrid approach that combines UAV imagery with satellite-derived bathymetry, providing a balance between coverage and detail.

Regardless of the resolution, flight planning plays a central role in ensuring data quality. Key parameters such as image overlap, both frontal (ideally $\geq 80\%$) and lateral ($\geq 60\%$), must be carefully managed to support 3D reconstruction, especially when working with SfM. Flight altitude, camera angle, and sensor settings must also be adapted to site conditions, including lighting and wind. For LiDAR systems, flight lines should be planned to guarantee even point distribution across the survey area.

Moreover, collecting ancillary data, such as tide levels, sun angle, and atmospheric conditions, is critical to contextualizing the survey and supporting accurate processing and interpretation. Recording this information during field operations allows for corrections and refinements that are especially important in shallow, optically variable environments.

Resuming, the resolution needs can be:

- High-resolution surveys (sub-meter): ideal for VR, habitat mapping, coastal engineering
→ Prefer SfM with high image overlap and GCPs
- Medium-resolution (1–2 m): suitable for coastal risk analysis
→ Use LiDAR or combine SfM with satellite-derived data

Accordingly, the survey planning checklist will include:

- Ensuring image overlap: $\geq 80\%$ frontal, $\geq 60\%$ lateral
- Deploying Ground Control Points (GCPs)
- Recording tide, light, and environmental conditions
- Planning flights during optimal weather and sun angles

In summary, resolution and survey design are deeply interlinked, and must be considered together. A clear understanding of the project's goals, environmental conditions, and technological options is essential to designing a UAV survey that delivers meaningful and reliable results.

7. Final Note on Aerial Uncrewed Vehicles (AUVs)

Recent advancements in autonomous UAVs (AUVs) are opening new possibilities in shallow water mapping. AUVs can perform automated, repeatable flight missions, enhancing consistency and safety in data acquisition. As these systems evolve, the integration of automated flight planning and improved data management tools makes UAVs increasingly attractive for use in dynamic or hard-to-reach coastal environments.

Deliverable 2.3 Technology Comparison Matrix

List of Sensors and Techniques for Bathymetric Data Collection in Shallow-Water Environments

Sensor Type	Sensor	Platform	Achievable DTM Resolution (Nearshore)	Survey Environment	Pros	Cons
Passive Sensors & Computational Techniques						
Optical	SDB (Satellite-Derived Bathymetry)	Satellite	~2 m	Air/Water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large coverage area, rapid mapping - Publicly available data (e.g., Sentinel-2) - Provides photorealistic imagery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accuracy depends on processing algorithms - Affected by environmental constraints (turbidity, clouds) - Computationally intensive
	SfM (Structure from Motion)	UAV	Sub-metric	Air/Water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost-effective, available with low-cost drones - Photorealistic visualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires ground control points (GCP) for validation - No established standards for data processing - Affected by water surface conditions (glint, waves)
Active Sensors						
Acoustic	MBES (Beamforming)	Vessel, ASV/USV, ROV	Sub-metric	Water	High accuracy and precision, meets international standards Dedicated software supports accurate data processing	Time-consuming due to small coverage per unit of time Requires immersion, limiting very shallow water use Not ideal for topographically complex seafloors
		Vessel	Sub-metric	Water	High-resolution capability Suitable for detailed bathymetric mapping	Similar limitations to MBES in very shallow water
	MPES (Hybrid)	Vessel	Sub-metric	Water	Enhanced accuracy through hybrid technology	It may require specialized processing
Optical	Bathymetric LiDAR	Airborne, UAV	Sub-metric	Air/Water	Covers large areas in short time High accuracy, meets international standards	Sensitive to environmental factors like turbidity and weather Data processing is time-consuming
	LLS (Laser Line Scanning)	Vessel, ROV	Sub-metric	Water	High resolution, useful for deep and complex environments Effective where MBES struggles	Data validation can be difficult Environmental conditions like turbidity impact performance

Notes:

- **Active sensors:** project waves (sound/light) onto the scene for data collection.
- **Passive sensors:** rely on ambient light or computational reconstruction.

- **MBES (Multi-Beam Echo-Sounder)** – Uses multiple sonar beams to map the seafloor with high accuracy.
- **PDBS (Phase Differencing Bathymetric Systems)** – Measures depth by analyzing phase shifts in sonar signals.
- **MPES (Multi-Phase Echo-Sounders)** – Hybrid system combining multiple acoustic techniques for enhanced bathymetry.
- **Bathymetric LiDAR** – Uses airborne laser pulses to measure underwater topography in clear waters.
- **LLS (Laser Line Scanning)** – High-resolution laser scanning system for underwater mapping, often ROV-mounted.
- **SDB (Satellite-Derived Bathymetry)** – Estimates water depth from satellite imagery using light penetration models.
- **SfM (Structure from Motion)** – Generates 3D models from overlapping 2D images, commonly captured by drones.

Note: the table has been adapted from Prampolini et al., 2020.

References

Prampolini M, Savini A., Foglini F., Soldati M. (2020) Seven Good Reasons for Integrating Terrestrial and Marine Spatial Datasets in Changing Environments. *Water* 2020, 12, 2221

Deliverable 2.4

Internal Technical Report by Orthodrone GmbH

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The second result of the BridgET project demonstrates the successful application of UAS (Uncrewed Aerial Systems) for high-resolution spatial data acquisition in shallow waters. Utilizing 100-megapixel metric medium-format cameras and (red) LiDAR, the project aimed to enhance existing datasets, achieve seamless data integration, and develop new methodologies for shallow water and bathymetry studies.

Aim:

The project aimed to utilize Uncrewed Aerial Systems (UAS) for the high-resolution spatial data acquisition of shallow waters. This involves the utilization of metric medium format cameras and LiDAR technology to enhance the quality of data collection. Additionally, the project improved existing data sets provided by partners, ensuring seamless data integration to achieve greater accuracy and completeness. A key focus was also on developing and validating new methods for analyzing shallow water environments and bathymetry.

T1 Site Selection and Critical Issues Need Analysis: The need analysis conducted for this project revealed several key challenges in data acquisition for shallow waters. First, users who collect data using Uncrewed Surface Vehicles (USV) or Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) often face difficulties in reaching the shore due to insufficient water depth. This limitation prevents comprehensive data collection in nearshore areas. Second, existing satellite imagery and other conventional remote sensing methods fail to provide the required resolution for accurate bathymetric and environmental assessments. Third, certain target areas are either difficult to access or pose safety risks, making traditional data acquisition methods inefficient or hazardous. Based on these findings, we judged the need for a new solution to be high. The proposed solution involves utilizing UAS equipped with different sensors to bridge the gap between existing methodologies and provide higher-resolution data than conventional platforms.

The data and methodologies developed in this project are beneficial to a wide range of stakeholders. Scientists can use high-resolution spatial data for environmental and geological studies. Environmental observers can utilize the data for monitoring. Local authorities can apply the insights for coastal management and hazard mitigation. The tourism sector can benefit from improved mapping and environmental assessments to support sustainable tourism initiatives and make famous places available to everybody by using VR as a tool for presentation. Additionally, natural hazard response teams can leverage this data for assessing risks in coastal and shallow water environments, aiding in disaster preparedness and response efforts.

The key locations selected for this project were chosen by the consortium based on the scientific need for high-resolution data, accessibility, and flight authorization. These factors ensured that the selected sites provided optimal conditions for data collection and methodological validation.

Santorini Red Beach, Greece

Sicily St. Tecla, and Isoli di Ciclopi, Italy

Coral reefs near Magoodhoo Island, Maldives

T2: Data Acquisition and Processing

The project employed a range of data acquisition methods tailored to the unique conditions of each study site. For Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry, a Phase One iXM100 metric medium-format camera system with a 35mm lens was employed. LiDAR data was collected using a RIEGL miniVUX-1UAV, both mounted on a DJI M300 RTK.

In Santorini, a combination of SfM and LiDAR was used to capture high-resolution spatial data. However, at the key site Red Beach, only LiDAR was deployed due to EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) restrictions and avoiding flying above uninvolved individuals, which limited the timeframe to sunset hours and therefore unsuitable light conditions for SfM.

Fig. 1: Red Beach, Detail in Greyscale (Intensity) LiDAR point cloud. ©Orthodrone.

In Sicily, for St. Tecla, both SfM and LiDAR were utilized. At Isoli di Ciclopi, only a short survey window was permitted, allowing for LiDAR acquisition only. However, our cooperation partner Daniel Carlson (Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon) conducted additional surveys outside Orthodrone's time frame. He acquired sonar data deploying a Squirm Tech Boogie Boat Uncrewed Surface Vehicle (USV) equipped with a Humminbird Helix 7 and performed SfM photogrammetry using an Autel Evo 2 Pro RTK. The USV with imaging sonar enabled access to shallow water areas that were otherwise challenging to reach, ensuring seamless data integration with multibeam surveys conducted by our partners.

Fig.2: Isoli di Ciclopi: Overlay of different surveying methods for seamless data: SfM (color), greyscale: sonar scan (Daniel Carlson) and LiDAR (red to yellow intensity point cloud) (Orthodrone) in GIS. ©Orthodrone.

For the Maldives, an integrated approach combining underwater and above-water SfM techniques was tested to find out if bathymetric mapping of the coral reef would be possible with this method. Additionally, SfM and LiDAR were used at the harbor site for teaching purposes.

Fig. 3: Colorized (based on SfM data) LiDAR 3D pointcloud of Magoodhoo Harbor. ©Orthodrone.

Acquired Datasets during summer schools:

Site Name	Short description	Date of Capture
Red Beach, Santorini, Greece	Red Beach – A cliff affected by erosion. Due to flight limitations, only LiDAR was used for surveying.	2022-10-11
Metaxa Mine, Santorini, Greece	Shoreline Mine Metaxa – A site where Structure from Motion (SfM) and LiDAR data were combined for analysis.	2022-10-10
Vlychada Beach, Santorini, Greece	Geological Site – Features volcanic stratigraphy, surveyed using SfM for future educational purposes.	2022-10-08
Santa Tecla, Sicily	Harbor Site – Includes a geologically important cliff and a historic tower. A combination of LiDAR and SfM was used.	2023-10-05
Isoli di Ciclopi, Sicily	Rock Formations (Small Islands) – Due to restrictive flight permit schedule, only LiDAR was conducted. SfM with a smaller UAS and a sonar mounted on an USV were used, in collaboration with Daniel Carlson, to integrate data seamlessly with our partner’s surveys.	2023-10-06
Magoodhoo Harbor, Maldives	Harbor at Magoodhoo Island, Faafu Atoll – A combination of LiDAR and SfM was applied for teaching purposes.	2024-11-22
Magoodhoo Reef, Maldives	Coral Reef Survey – Surveyed from the air using LiDAR for shoreline, along with above-water and underwater SfM. Due to weather conditions and boat availability, only selected sections were surveyed.	2024-11-14

Tab. 01: BridgET data sets acquired during summer schools by Orthodrone.

Methodology and achieved resolution of data sets:

Site Name	SfM (Land)	LiDAR (red)	SfM (Water)	Resolution	
				SfM: GSD in cm	LiDAR: pt/m ²
Red Beach, Santorini, Greece				Min. 30	
Metaxa Mine, Santorini, Greece				1 cm	Min. 50
Vlychada Beach, Santorini, Greece				Still in progress	
Santa Tecla, Sicily				0.5cm	Min. 60
Isoli di Ciclopi, Sicily				Still in progress	
Magoodhoo Harbor, Maldives				Still in progress	Min. 50
Magoodhoo, Reef, Maldives				Still in progress	

Tab.02: Green: Data with this method available. Resolution calculated based on point cloud.

Several innovative approaches were introduced to enhance data accuracy and efficiency. A key advancement was the combination of multiple data collection methods to improve precision. The use of an USV equipped with sonar proved to be a highly effective solution for conducting bathymetric surveys in shallow waters. Additionally, the integration of underwater SfM with geolocation calibration from above-water sources was tested. The aim was to improve spatial accuracy and seamless data integration.

Data processing was optimized to reduce turnaround times and improve overall efficiency. The use of LiDAR data, which was colorized with SfM imagery, significantly expedited the processing workflow. Furthermore, seamless data integration was achieved by applying precise location calibration with Ground Control Points (GCPs), ensuring high accuracy in the final datasets.

T3: Seamless Data and Virtual Reality:

The project successfully produced high-resolution and accurate datasets, enhancing the overall quality of spatial data acquisition. However, some issues arose in Sicily due to a sensor failure and the unavailability of RTK and PPK correction data from nearby stations, which impacted real-time data accuracy, leading to a delay in the processing of the Isoli di Ciclopi dataset. In general, the use of Structure from Motion (SfM) techniques captured underwater structures in rocky areas in good light conditions and calm sea. However, it proved to be less effective in sandy beach environments, where underwater features were more challenging to distinguish, also caused by the movement of waves.

The project achieved reasonably seamless data integration for Santorini and Sicily (Isoli di Ciclopi). The combination of LiDAR, SfM, and sonar data ensured a continuous and highly detailed dataset across various water depths at Sicily, successfully bridging gaps between different survey methods. Virtual

Reality applications were successfully implemented in Santorini and were actively utilized for educational purposes. The VR models provided an immersive way to analyze and interpret the collected data, enhancing both research, dissemination and teaching methodologies.

T4: Best Practices

A multi-method approach that combines green and red LiDAR, above-water SfM, and underwater SfM is recommended to achieve optimal results in shallow water data acquisition. Using Ground Control Points (GCPs) on land significantly enhances accuracy by ensuring seamless data integration with other datasets obtained from different platforms. For shallow water mapping, bathymetric LiDAR is particularly effective in capturing precise depth measurements. Furthermore, combining above-water and underwater SfM with an above-water GPS solution ensures better spatial alignment and georeferencing of the datasets. Lastly, integrating SfM with LiDAR technology accelerates data processing, allowing for faster production of high-quality data deliverables. Accompanied by an USV with a sonar, seamless data can be guaranteed. For the validation using on-land GCPs and georeferencing by utilizing above and underwater SfM for the near-shore and coastline is highly recommended.

Outcome

The project successfully generated 11 datasets using different methodologies, providing comprehensive insights into shallow water environments. For each summer school one dataset is available for scientific and teaching purposes (Red Beach, Santorini, St. Tecla, Sicily, Magoodhoo Harbor, Maldives) under a creative commons license (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 DEED).

As a result of this project, Orthodrone developed a novel methodology for integrating above-water and underwater Structure from Motion (SfM). Additionally, plans have been established to integrate bathymetric LiDAR onto UAS platforms, further enhancing data collection capabilities. Through this initiative, Orthodrone has expanded its academic and professional networks, fostering new research collaborations. During the summer school in Sicily, a collaboration was established with researcher Daniel Carlson (Hereon) for an USV solution equipped with sonar, further improving data collection methods. Moreover, the project enabled direct engagement with students, some of whom may become future employees in the field.

The project provided students with exposure to Uncrewed Aerial System (UAS) technology and its diverse applications. Additionally, students gained valuable insights into startup development and career opportunities within and beyond academia, equipping them with knowledge and experience relevant to their future professional endeavors. Students played an active role in various stages of the project, including data acquisition, classroom discussions, and interactive question-and-answer sessions. Their direct participation contributed to both their learning experience and the success of the research efforts.

The findings and methodologies developed in this project have led to a new collaboration with the University of Kiel for research on above-and-below water SfM studies. Furthermore, a follow-up project within the BridgET consortium is planned, ensuring the continuation and further development of these research efforts.

Outreach & Dissemination activities:

The BridgET project was presented at the German Hydrographic Association (GHA) annual meeting, held from June 20–21, 2023, in Berlin. During this event, Dr. Clara Drummer from Orthodrone delivered a presentation highlighting the applications of UAS in hydrography. The presentation emphasized the importance of seamless data integration and demonstrated how UAS technology can bridge the gap between offshore and onshore data collection. Additionally, challenges associated with near-shore shallow water bathymetry were discussed, along with the future potential of UAS-based hydrographic

surveys. The use of UAS for both training and data acquisition in future summer school programs was also highlighted. Furthermore, Orthodrone showcased LiDAR and SfM-derived 3D datasets on several international exhibitions such as the Intergeo Tradeshow and at the European Geosciences Union (EGU) Meetings in Vienna in 2023 and 2024, making the collected data visible to a vast international audience of research experts from various disciplines.